

Are voter rolls suitable sampling frames for household surveys?

Evidence from India

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Abstract

We examine the use of publicly available voter rolls for household survey sampling as an alternative to household listings or field-based sampling methods. Using voter rolls for sampling can save most of the cost of constructing a sampling frame relative to a household listing, but there is limited evidence about their accuracy and completeness. We conducted a household listing in 13 polling stations in India comprising 2,416 households across four states, and compared the listing to voter rolls for the same polling stations. We show that voter rolls include 91% of the households found in the household listing. Coverage is higher in rural areas (96%) compared to urban areas (78%). We conduct simulations to show that sampling from voter rolls produces estimates of household-level economic variables with minimal bias. These results suggest that voter rolls may be suitable for constructing household sampling frames, particularly in rural India.

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I. Introduction

When making policy decisions, policymakers often rely on representative population statistics. Generating such statistics, however, can be expensive and time-consuming. If sample surveys were cheaper and faster to conduct, policymakers could commission more surveys, leading to more decisions informed by data.

A large component of the cost of surveys is the cost of constructing a comprehensive sampling frame from which the researcher can sample units (households, individuals, firms) to survey. The gold standard for constructing sampling frames for household surveys is a “household listing”. In a household listing, surveyors map the sampled area, then go door-to-door to list all the households residing within the area, and finally draw a probability sample from this comprehensive list. Because each household has to be mapped and enumerated, this process is costly and time-consuming.

Quasi-random alternatives to household listing, such as “right-hand rule,” “spin-the-pen,” and other methods developed as part of the World Health Organization’s Expanded Programme on Immunization (EPI), have also been widely used by public health and social science researchers (Bennett et al, 1991; Hadler et al, 2004). They may be cheaper and faster than household listing, but are prone to bias (Lemeshow and Robinson, 1985; Shannon et al, 2012).

To avoid the cost of household listing while mitigating the risk of bias inherent in quasi-random methods, researchers across disciplines in India have turned to lists of voters, or “voter rolls,” to construct sampling frames (Abraham et al, 2018; Banerjee et al, 2014; Dalal, 2008; Keshavamurthy et al, 2019; Khera, 2008; Lokniti, 2009; Neggers, 2018; Shukla et al, 2002). Voter rolls are publicly available, which reduces the time and cost required to construct the sampling frame. Given universal adult franchise in India, voter rolls are expected to cover every voting-age citizen of that area. Voter rolls are regularly updated by the Election Commission of India (ECI), a constitutional authority that is well-regarded for independence and efficient conduct of the largest democratic elections in the world (Kapur et al, 2018; Shani, 2017). The ECI has instituted several supervisory and community checks to ensure that the voter rolls include all voting-age adults (ECI, 2020)

However, recent research has cast doubt on the quality of Indian voter rolls. Voter rolls seem to be updated less frequently than mandated (Peisakhin, 2012). Bureaucratic hurdles may lead to the exclusion of migrants from voter rolls, and the application process can be opaque, corrupt and biased against the urban poor (Peisakhin 2012; Gaikwad and Nellis 2020). Errors in voter rolls may be particularly large in cities with high rates of in-migration (Janaagraha, 2015, 2020) and rural areas with high rates of out-migration (Verma et al, 2019). Researchers comparing voter rolls with India’s Population Census estimate high exclusion for certain demographic groups such as women (Roy and Sopariwala, 2019) and Muslims (Shariff and Saifullah, 2018). Given these findings, it is important for researchers and policymakers who rely on samples drawn from voter rolls to know the extent of errors in the voter rolls, and to know how these errors bias any resulting sample drawn using voter rolls as a sampling frame.

In this paper, we document the extent of exclusion errors in the voter rolls in several locations in northern India. We randomly sampled thirteen polling stations from four northern states. Four of these polling stations are located in urban areas, nine in rural areas. In each location, we compiled the most recent voter rolls, as well as conducted a complete household listing. We then matched individuals enumerated in the household listing to individuals listed on the voter rolls, using either the voter ID number (if provided), or other personal information such as name, age, gender, and family relationships. This matching allows us to calculate the aggregate household exclusion error rates, and to investigate how these errors vary with urban or rural status, gender, age, caste, and religion. Finally, we simulated 1,000 random draws from voter rolls and compared the resulting sample estimates to the true population values based on the household listing.

We find that voter rolls have low household exclusion errors: across our study area, voter rolls include at least one member from 91 percent of the households. Coverage is significantly higher in rural polling stations (96 percent) compared to the urban polling stations (78 percent). Exclusion from voter rolls does not appear to vary by a household's religion or socioeconomic status, though wealthier, higher-caste households in urban areas are more likely to be excluded. When we compare estimates from randomly drawing household samples from the voter rolls with population values from the household listing, we find that the two sets of estimates are within 2 percentage points of each other for a range of asset and demographic indicators.

While these results are not statistically representative of the states from which we have sampled the polling stations, to our knowledge this is the most robust evidence to date that voter rolls are a viable alternative for generating household sampling frames in India. These findings are further strengthened by a separate field exercise that we conducted in Rajasthan in 2017, described in the online appendix, where we examined the completeness of voter rolls and found similar rates of inclusion.

This paper contributes to several literatures. First, we build on the literature that explores optimal ways to construct household sampling frames, especially in low and middle-income countries (LMICs). Several of these studies have called into question the robustness of field-based sampling methods included as part of the EPI program (Chao et al, 2012; Grais et al, 2007; Milligan et al, 2004). More recently, studies have explored GIS or satellite-based sampling methods (Awuah et al, 2017; Guo et al, 2016; Himelein et al, 2016) but these papers have focused on limited geographies and contexts.

Second, we contribute to the literature on the quality of voter rolls for household sampling. A rich literature documents errors in voter registration records in the United States using phone surveys (Shino et al 2020) and mailed surveys (Ansolabehere et al 2010), and links errors in records to subsequent exclusion from voter lists (Merivaki 2020). Some researchers have used voter lists as sampling frames for web and phone surveys (e.g. Shino et al 2022). While these studies provide insights into using voter lists for sampling in contexts where voter registration is passive, our study occurs in a context where voter registration is active and all voting age adults should be included in voter rolls. Yet several studies have cast doubt on the completeness and accuracy of voter rolls in India in both urban (Janaagraha, 2015, 2020) and rural areas (Verma et al, 2019). Other studies have compared the number of adults reported by the

Indian Population Census and registered voters in voter rolls to highlight potential exclusion errors in voter rolls (Retnakumar, 2009; Roy and Sopariwala, 2019). Our paper is the first direct comparison of voter rolls in India with independent listings of individuals in the same polling stations to estimate exclusion errors.

Finally, we provide tools and recommendations for researchers interested in working with voter rolls and with Indian administrative records recorded in the Devanagari script. We share our code for a “fuzzy matching” algorithm to match Hindi names across our household listing and voter rolls. We also demonstrate that our algorithm, which has a high true match rate and a low false match rate, significantly outperforms alternative off-the-shelf algorithms.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In the next section, we describe how voter rolls are constructed and how they can be used for household sample surveys. Then, we describe how we collected our data, and our methodology for matching individual records and subsequently estimating household exclusion rates. Finally, we present and discuss the results.

II. Sampling from Voter Rolls in India

1. Voter rolls in India

Each Indian state is divided into national and state constituencies, and each constituency into polling stations. All voters registered in an area vote at the same location, usually at a school or primary healthcare centre. In urban areas, a polling station is composed of adjacent streets. In rural areas, the polling station could be an entire village or part of a village. Since polling stations are created exclusively for the purpose of managing elections, they do not map neatly onto other administrative units such as villages or wards. The number of voters at a polling station should not exceed 1,200 in rural areas and 1,400 in urban areas (PTI, 2017).

The Indian Constitution guarantees the right to vote to all citizens aged 18 and above. To be able to vote, citizens must appear on the voter roll – the list of registered voters – of their respective constituencies. The ECI is responsible for preparing, maintaining and revising the voter rolls, with the Electoral Registration Officer (ERO) and the Booth Level Officers (BLO) in charge of implementation at the level of the constituency and the polling station, respectively.

The voter registration process, in theory, should ensure that every citizen 18 years or older is listed on the voter rolls of their respective constituency. Every five years, EROs and their staff are mandated to conduct ‘intensive revisions’ of voter rolls, during which they visit every household in their constituency to register eligible citizens. Voter rolls are also updated annually to add newly eligible voters and those who have recently moved into the area, and to delete names of those who have died or shifted out of the area. Citizens can initiate the process of registering to vote, for instance if they come of age between registration drives or move to a new location, by submitting an application to the local registration office.

2. How to sample using voter rolls

Researchers seeking population-representative statistics must have a comprehensive list of the population from which to sample, or a process that generates near-random samples. In settings such as India that lack readily-available lists of residents for a given area, researchers often resort to generating household listings, with survey teams mapping the sampled areas and going door-to-door to construct a list of households. While such lists provide a robust basis for drawing probability samples, they are expensive to construct. Alternative in-field sampling techniques, such as randomly selecting a point in a sampled area, surveying the nearest household, and then proceeding to every *n*th household to the right (the “right-hand rule”) are difficult to implement consistently across areas and survey teams, and can lead to non-representative samples (Lemeshow and Robinson, 1985; Shannon et al, 2012).

In India, voter rolls may provide near-comprehensive household listings that facilitate consistent sampling across sampled areas and generate representative samples. The latest voter rolls for each polling station can be found on the website of each state’s Chief Electoral Officer. The voter roll includes the polling station address, the number of voters registered in the polling station, the date of the last update, a map showing the geographic extent of the polling station, and details of each voter.

Figure 1 shows a typical (mock) entry in the voter roll. The entry includes the voter’s name, their relative’s name (usually parent or spouse), their age at the time of the last update, gender, and a house number. The house number is based on co-residence within the same structure and is typically assigned by the registration officer, rather than representing the street address. The number in the top left corner is the voter’s serial number in the voter roll; the alphanumeric sequence in the top right is the voter’s unique ID. The voter’s photo is included on their voter ID card and in the ECI’s database, but not in publicly available voter rolls.

Figure 1: Mock Voter Roll Entry

1	AAA9999999
Name : RAJ KUMAR Father's Name : RAM KUMAR House Number : 18 Age : 35 Sex : MALE	Photo is Available

Researchers using voter rolls to construct household sampling frames might sample villages and urban wards from administrative lists and then attempt to match the corresponding polling stations. However, matching may be inexact since a village or ward may have multiple polling stations, and a polling station may include parts from multiple villages or wards.

Instead, we recommend sampling electoral administrative units directly. Most state websites publish the number of voters per assembly constituency and polling station, which facilitates sampling clusters with probability proportional to size, or to construct post-sampling weights.

Once clusters have been selected, we recommend randomly sampling voters from the voter rolls and instructing enumerators to find and list the households to which the sampled voters belong. Although

voter rolls include house numbers, we found that voters with the same house number often belong to multiple households, and members of the same household are often listed under different house numbers in the voter rolls. In some voter rolls, house numbers are missing altogether. We recommend bypassing these issues by sampling voters directly. To obtain household-level estimates, weights based on the number of voters in each household are needed to correct for unequal probabilities of selection and recover unbiased population estimates.

III. Methodology and Data Collection

1. Polling station sample and household listing

Our sample includes thirteen polling stations across four states: Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, and Uttar Pradesh. Historically, these states have lagged in human development indicators compared to other Indian states, making them a high priority for development policy and programs, and a key geography for high-quality sample surveys to inform policy. These states include over a third of India's population. Although our sample is not large enough to be statistically representative of the population of these states, we selected these states to maximize the population for which we could make indicative claims.

From each of the four states, we randomly sampled two assembly constituencies. In national and state elections in India, some constituencies are "reserved" for candidates belonging to the most marginalized groups: Scheduled Castes (SC) and Scheduled Tribes (ST). While only candidates who belong to an SC or ST can compete in these constituencies, all voters in the constituency, including SC/ST and non-SC/ST, are eligible to vote in the elections. We hypothesized that unreserved constituencies may have voter rolls of differing quality from reserved constituencies given different incentives to register voters from upper and lower castes across constituency types. Thus, we stratified by constituency type, yielding a sample of ten assembly constituencies [5 General, 3 SC, and 2 ST] across the four states.

Next, we randomly sampled two polling stations from each assembly constituency, resulting in a sample of 20 polling stations. Of these, we collected data from 13 polling stations. Our data collection period (November-December 2019) coincided with the passing of the Citizenship Amendment Act 2019, which provided a path for Indian citizenship for non-Muslims from neighboring Muslim-majority countries. The act, which was championed by the ruling Hindu nationalist Bharatiya Janata Party, was seen as discriminating on the basis of religion, and sparked widespread, violent, and sometimes deadly protests throughout the country. As the political crisis unfolded, our field staff were increasingly denied access to respondents' voter ID data (which had become highly sensitive as a citizenship document), and in some cases, pressured to halt data collection by local political groups. Because of safety concerns for our field staff, we stopped data collection after 14 polling stations. We were unable to resume data collection after the crisis since it was prohibitively costly to relaunch field operations. Since our decision was driven by an unexpected political shock, and not by particular characteristics of the polling stations themselves, we do not expect that the remaining six polling stations would have substantially different results from those included in our final sample.

However, four of the six unsurveyed polling stations are in a single state - Rajasthan - raising concerns that our findings may be ambiguous for that state, since we have data from only two of the six polling stations that were initially sampled from there. While we cannot rule out the possibility that the four unsurveyed polling stations would have substantively different findings, we do have data from an earlier field exercise conducted by our team in six villages and urban wards in Rajasthan that supplements the findings in this paper. As described in the online appendix, we conducted a similar exercise to assess voter rolls in the Ajmer district of Rajasthan by comparing publicly-available rolls with an independent household listing. We do not combine the Ajmer results with the current study since the methodologies differ slightly: in Ajmer, we sampled villages and urban wards instead of polling stations and used a shorter survey instrument during household listing. However, as described in the Discussion section, the results of the two studies are remarkably consistent, giving us more confidence that the exclusion of polling stations from Rajasthan in the current study is unlikely to substantively affect our findings.

In our analysis below, we exclude one other polling station where we attempted to collect data. One sampled urban polling station in Madhya Pradesh covered an area that differed from the boundaries denoted on the map provided by the ECI. We discovered this issue after examining the data and finding that a majority of residents surveyed were registered in adjacent polling stations. As a result, we dropped this polling station from the analysis.

We examined voter rolls from polling stations that were adjacent to the other polling stations in our sample and confirmed that a similar issue did not occur elsewhere. While we believe that the problem with inaccurate boundary delimitation is rare, it raises a potential caution to researchers using voter rolls for sampling: in some polling stations, voters may be found outside the area denoted in the ECI-provided map.

Within each sampled polling station we attempted to list every household. Our team located a community leader, usually the BLO in charge of maintaining the updated voter lists for that polling station, to understand the boundaries of the polling station. Our field team would ask the community leader to confirm the boundaries of the polling station, and reconcile any discrepancies with the map printed on the voter rolls of that polling station. The field team then systematically walked through the polling station, enumerated every dwelling structure in the polling station, and listed and interviewed each household in every structure. We defined a household to be a group of people normally living together and taking food from a common kitchen (at least six months of the last year), consistent with the definition used by the United Nations (UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs Statistics Division, 2017) and the Indian National Sample Survey Office (National Sample Survey Office, 2016).

We enumerated 2,416 households. Of these, we collected data on 2,369 or 98.1% of the enumerated households, which included 7,769 voting-age individuals. We collected the same information from respondents that is listed in voter roll entries. We also collected information on asset ownership, caste, religion, primary occupation of the household, and household size.

2. Matching listing data to voter rolls

In order to compare the ground-truth household listing data with voter roll data, we matched eligible voters identified in our listing with entries of registered voters listed on the voter rolls.

We first merged individuals across the two datasets using their voter ID number. 44 percent of matches were based on voter ID. Where the respondent did not provide their voter ID number, or if the voter ID number did not match with a valid ID, we “fuzzy matched” names and other identifying information like gender, age, marital status, and whether individuals were listed in the same house number as other matched individuals. Fewer than 10 percent of the matches were based on the exact same spelling of the individual’s name and their relative’s name; 46 percent matches were based on fuzzy name matching and different pieces of information provided in the voter rolls. We describe our matching algorithm, with 125 discrete merges of the two datasets, in the online appendix.

3. Analytical approach

We estimate household exclusion by calculating the percentage of households in our listing that have at least one individual who matched to an individual on the voter roll of their polling station.

Next, we assess whether sampling from voter rolls can produce unbiased estimates of household characteristics by simulating the sampling procedure. Since house numbers in voter rolls are inconsistently defined and sometimes missing, we sample households by sampling individuals from voter rolls without replacement, selecting their corresponding household until the desired number of households is reached, and then applying household weights to correct for unequal probabilities of selection. To calculate weights, we asked the household head to report the number of registered voters in their household. Thus, our sampling weight for each household is:

$$w_{ip} = [\Pr(\text{select } hh \ i \ \text{in } ps \ p)]^{-1}, \text{ where}$$
$$\Pr(\text{select } hh \ i \ \text{in } ps \ p) = (\# \text{ households sampled in } p) * \frac{(\# \text{ voters reported in } i)}{(\# \text{ voters in } p\text{'s voter roll})}$$

In theory, these weights should correctly account for different numbers of voters in each household, and thus unequal probabilities of selection. But if self-reported voter counts are inaccurate and errors are correlated with household characteristics, then applying household weights based on these self-reported numbers may worsen bias. We simulate the sampling method and assess how estimates using these approximate weights compare to true means.

IV. Results

1. Household-level voter roll exclusion

Table 1 shows the percent of households in each polling station with at least one individual found in voter rolls. Across thirteen polling stations, voter rolls include at least one member from 91 percent of the households. Household match rates are significantly higher for the nine rural polling stations (96 percent) than for the four urban polling stations (78 percent). The lower urban match rates are largely

driven by one urban polling station in Bihar where only 63% of households had a voter match in the voter rolls; excluding this polling station, the urban match rate increases to 88% and the overall match rate increases to 94%.

Table 1: Household Match Rates by Polling Station

State	PS	Urban/Rural	Reservation	Total HH	Matched HH	Matched %
Bihar	1	Urban	GEN	180	157	87%
Bihar	2	Urban	GEN	264	165	63%
Bihar	3	Rural	SC	252	244	97%
Bihar	4	Rural	SC	224	219	98%
Madhya Pradesh	5	Urban	GEN	126	111	88%
Madhya Pradesh	6	Rural	GEN	130	120	92%
Madhya Pradesh	7	Rural	ST	192	183	95%
Madhya Pradesh	8	Rural	ST	206	193	94%
Madhya Pradesh	9	Urban	GEN	84	74	88%
Rajasthan	10	Rural	GEN	171	160	94%
Rajasthan	11	Rural	GEN	249	243	98%
Uttar Pradesh	12	Rural	SC	146	144	99%
Uttar Pradesh	13	Rural	SC	145	136	94%
Total				2369	2149	91%

We examine match rates by subgroups and post the full results in the online appendix. While match rates are lower for upper caste households, households in the top wealth quartile, and households without a ration card, this is partly explained by urban areas having lower match rates and the fact that such households are more likely to live in urban areas. In rural polling stations, match rates are comparable across all groups; no between-group differences are statistically significant at the 5% level. In urban polling stations, upper-caste Hindu households in the top wealth quartile have slightly lower match rates than other groups ($p < 0.05$).

2. Estimation using household samples from voter rolls

Given low but non-zero exclusion rates, we examine whether voter rolls can be used to construct household samples that produce estimates with low bias. We compare mean values for all households in our household listing with households that have at least one matched registered voter for sixteen characteristics collected in our household survey. Any differences in means reflects bias due to exclusion

error. In the online appendix we report differences for all variables in terms of raw percentages and standard deviations.

Across all polling stations, bias is less than 2 percentage points or 0.05 SD for all variables. Bias is larger in urban polling stations, where the difference in means between all households and matched households is greater than 4 percentage points for two variables. In rural polling stations, differences in means never exceed 1 percentage point, or 0.02 SD, for any variable.

Although this suggests that voter rolls can be used to obtain a representative sample of households in the polling station, unbiased estimation also depends on calculating accurate weights for the sampled households. To investigate whether our household weights based on self-reported number of registered voters yield unbiased estimates, we simulated our recommended random sampling procedure. We randomly sampled individuals from the voter rolls and selected their corresponding household. If an individual was not matched with a name in our household listing, then we assumed that that person could not be found and we drew again. If an individual matched with a name in a household that had already been selected, then we discarded that draw and drew again until we found 10 distinct households per polling station. With this sample we estimated mean values for each of the 16 variables listed above, weighting each household inversely to the number of registered voters in the household as reported by the household head. We repeated this process 1,000 times and calculated the average simulated mean estimates.

Our simulated sample estimates are close to true means. For the full sample, differences between weighted estimates and true means never exceeds 4 percentage points for any of the 16 variables.

VI. Discussion

In this paper, we assessed the suitability of using voter rolls for constructing household sampling frames. Since using voter rolls to sample households is a cheaper alternative than conducting a household listing, and researchers already use them for sampling in India, this paper presents new evidence on their accuracy and completeness for household surveys.

Based on our findings of low household exclusion and low bias in sampling estimates, we recommend that researchers could use voter rolls for household sampling. Since we do not find systematic exclusion of marginalised groups, voter rolls are also a promising household sampling frame for research examining program delivery to marginalised groups. Researchers may consider using voter rolls for sampling individuals, though given systematic exclusion of certain groups, we recommend sampling households, visiting those households and sampling from all members, rather than sampling individuals directly from voter rolls (see the Online Appendix for individual-level matching results). Given higher variance in exclusion rates across urban polling stations in our sample, we recommend caution in using voter rolls for sampling households in urban areas.

Using voter rolls can lead to cost savings. We found that the cost of creating a sampling frame for one polling station using voter rolls was 86% less than conducting a household listing, since survey costs for household listing were greater than data entry costs for digitizing voter rolls.

For researchers interested in using voter rolls for sampling in India, we have assembled a guide with practical advice for finding and downloading voter rolls, processing and extracting relevant information, and selecting a household sample (IDinsight Voter Rolls FAQ, 2020). We also share our algorithm for fuzzy matching names transliterated from Devanagari to English, which has applications for processing and merging Indian government records beyond voter rolls. In the online appendix, we show that our matching algorithm performs favorably to off-the-shelf fuzzy matching software in terms of both true match rate and false match rate.

Our results are consistent with findings from an earlier field exercise conducted by our team in 2017, where we examined the completeness of voter rolls in five villages and one urban ward in the Ajmer district of Rajasthan: in that study, 92% of households had at least one member in the voter rolls, and the household match rate for urban areas (84%) was lower than the household match rate for rural areas (93%).

Limitations and areas of further research

There are several limitations to our study. Our results are not statistically representative of all polling stations in the selected states but are only indicative of voter roll quality in those states. While we find a difference in exclusion errors across urban and rural polling stations, our sample size was not large enough to pinpoint drivers of this difference.

Further research would be useful to assess the accuracy and completeness of voter rolls in other regions in India, and in other countries. Given high variance in exclusion rates across urban polling stations, it would also be valuable to examine the mechanisms that explain this variation, such that researchers may be able to more easily predict the quality of voter rolls in new areas.

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